

Supplementary Material for

**Conformal Prediction for ECG Interpretation:
A Study on Human-AI Collaboration in Clinical
Decision Support**

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A Supplementary Material

A.1 Description of the ECG database

Participants interacted with 20 Electrocardiogram (ECG) traces meticulously selected by a senior cardiologist from the ECG Wave-Maven repository based on their complexity. The difficulty of these cases was assessed using the original scale from the Wave-Maven repository, providing a standardized measure of complexity.

To facilitate analysis, we categorized the cases into two groups based on their difficulty level: “Lower” complexity for cases with a difficulty level of 2 or below and “Higher” complexity for cases with a difficulty level above 2.

The selected cases cover a broad spectrum of ECG findings, ranging from normal to pathological traces, including conduction and rhythm abnormalities, ischemia/infarction patterns, and typical changes in cardiomyopathies. In addition to the selection and evaluation of cases, these have also been translated into Portuguese by a senior Portuguese cardiologist, as they were initially documented in English. The same cardiologist provided detailed textual explanations for each diagnosis, ensuring adherence to standard clinical best practices and facilitating comprehensive understanding for all participants.

A.2 Questionnaire implementation

We used a multi-page online questionnaire hosted on the LimeSurvey platform (version 5.6.3). Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show an illustrative presentation of the questionnaire workflow for single- and set-valued support, respectively.

Single-valued support protocol

Man, 52 years old, brought by ambulance to the Emergency Department.

12-lead ECG exam

Page 1

The model predicts with 26% confidence the patient has *“Anterolateral STEMI, with possible prior inferior infarction”*.

After observing the diagnosis proposed by the AI system, do you agree with the recommendation, or do you want to provide an alternative diagnosis?

I agree.

I disagree.

Please write your alternative diagnosis in this box.

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The model predicts with 26% confidence the patient has *“Anterolateral STEMI, with possible prior inferior infarction”*.

Textual explanation provided by the AI system: Sinus rhythm (90 BPM) and ST segment elevation in I, aVL, V2-V6. ST segment depression in III and aVF. Incipient Q waves in V3-V6; low amplitude R waves in III and aVF and minimal Q waves in II.

After observing the textual explanation produced by the AI system, did you change your opinion regarding the diagnosis you issued previously?

No, I confirm my previous diagnosis.

Yes, I change my previous diagnosis to the AI system diagnosis

Yes, I change my previous diagnosis to an alternate diagnosis

Please write your alternative diagnosis in this box.

Fig. 1. Illustrative presentation of the questionnaire workflow for single-valued support. Participants are first shown a patient description accompanied by an ECG trace. On this same page, they make their initial decision supported by a single-valued prediction, which includes a confidence percentage. On the second page, participants receive a textual explanation. Subsequently, they are asked whether they want to maintain their initial decision or switch to an alternative option, leading to their final decision.

Set-valued support protocol

Man, 52 years old, brought by ambulance to the Emergency Department.

12-lead ECG exam

Page 1

The model predicts with 95% confidence that the correct diagnosis is one of the following options:

- *Acute pericarditis*, or
- *Anterolateral STEMI, with possible prior inferior infarction*, or
- *Pulmonary thromboembolism*

After observing the possible diagnoses proposed by the AI system, what is your choice?

Acute pericarditis

Anterolateral STEMI, with possible prior inferior infarction

Pulmonary thromboembolism

Other:

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The model predicts with 95% confidence that the correct diagnosis is one of the following options:

- *Acute pericarditis*, or
- *Anterolateral STEMI, with possible prior inferior infarction*, or
- *Pulmonary thromboembolism*

Textual explanation provided by the AI system: Sinus rhythm (90 BPM) and ST segment elevation in I, aVL, V2-V6. ST segment depression in III and aVF. Incipient Q waves in V3-V6; low amplitude R waves in III and aVF and minimal Q waves in II.

After observing the textual explanation produced by the AI system, did you change your opinion regarding the diagnosis you issued previously?

No, I confirm my previous diagnosis.

Yes, I want to issue a new diagnosis

- Acute pericarditis
- Anterolateral STEMI, with possible prior inferior infarction
- Pulmonary thromboembolism

Other:

Fig. 2. Illustrative presentation of the questionnaire workflow for set-valued support. Participants are first shown a patient description accompanied by an ECG trace. On this same page, they make their initial decision supported by a set-valued prediction, which includes a set of possible predictions where there is a 95% probability that the correct diagnosis was among them. On the second page, participants receive a textual explanation. Subsequently, they are asked whether they want to maintain their initial decision or switch to an alternative option, leading to their final decision.

A.3 Recruitment and sample description

Participants were recruited from the mailing list of the Portuguese Society of Cardiology. To partake in the study, each participant was assigned a unique token identifier, which they received through an individual invitation email. Furthermore, we gathered information about their years of experience as cardiologists (referred to as professional experience), categorized into three classes by the years of regular clinical practice (less than 5 years; between 5 and 10 years; and more than 10 years).

In our analysis, we stratified the participants into two broader groups based on their professional experience: ≤ 10 years, encompassing participants in the early to mid-stages of their medical careers, and > 10 years, encompassing the more experienced clinicians. This stratification was chosen to create more balanced groups, while also acknowledging the skewness towards participants with more than 10 years of experience, as can be observed in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive sample stratification by type of support and years of professional experience. Numbers between brackets in subtotal cells indicate the ratio for each stratification category.

	Single-valued	Set-valued	Subtotal
Professional Experience			
Less than 5 years	2	2	4 (.06)
Between 5 and 10 years	6	10	16 (.26)
More than 10 years	19	23	42 (.68)
Subtotal	27 (0.44)	35 (0.56)	62